

Journey mapping interview guide

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Part 1: Informing the participants

We started by sending personal emails to invite people to participate in the research, and with a Doodle link to select a suitable interview time. Once the participants have selected an interview time, the PI updates the calendar invitation, including a data privacy note and instructions for the pre-assignment.

Part 2: Designing the journey map

Biographical and reflective journey mapping is an increasingly important method in service management and experience design, as it addresses the processual and experiential aspects of service processes as seen from the customer's viewpoint (Følstad and Kvale, 2018). The method emphasizes interactions with the service throughout the process and enables participatory and co-design of the services (Rosenbaum et al., 2017).

The resulting journey map allows designers to better understand the experiences and touchpoints of a specific service. Often the process of creating a journey map is non-linear. Discussing one aspect of the journey may spark a thought about an earlier touchpoint or an insight about a different area of the service interaction. It is helpful to let the user know that this messiness is normal and a part of the process to reduce any anxiety and facilitate a creative, curious exploration of their interaction with the service.

We employ the journey mapping method to study doctoral study processes from the doctoral candidate's perspective. Journey mapping is not a commonly used method in higher education research: Turner (2015) studied four early-career supervisors and identified that unrealized supervisory expectations, student-supervisor relationships, and commitment were the common challenges in experienced doctoral supervision. Robinette (2024) examined the use of journey maps in teaching to strengthen students' self-reflection.

The workshops were organized in person or online using Zoom and Miro platforms. Before the workshop, the participants were asked to reflect on their doctoral thesis journey and collect necessary documents, such as notes and diaries. Each participant produced their own journey map: first, they were asked to document activities, milestones, resources, persons, touchpoints, and other observations of their journey into individual sticky notes and organize them into chronological order. Next, the participant graded their observations following Nilsson's classification (Nilsson et al., 2016) from -3 indicating the strongest negative impact (cancelling or making thesis work impossible) to +3 indicating the strongest positive impact (the action is inextricably linked to progress). Each participant is asked to visualize and construct their doctoral journey into an online Miro board:

"Kindly reflect on the experiences of your entire doctoral journey, from the moment you applied for the study right or started discussing your interest to the day of getting the degree. We are

interested in your experiences: activities, feelings, actions, milestones, persons, and also the ones outside work, but what contributed to the journey.”

PI has created a template for Miro and duplicates a personal copy for every participant.

Part 3: Journey mapping pre-assignment

A Miro board includes a journey map template with easy-access instructions, empty sticky notes, and arrows (Figure 1). The instructions consist of three main parts. No guidelines for the amount of text or the number of notes are set.

The interviewer must prepare by finding the interviewee’s doctoral dissertation and checking information for the background questions, such as the number of supervisors and articles in the thesis.

Part 4: Personal interview

Each interview is organized online in Zoom and scheduled for 90 minutes. We start by introducing ourselves and the research aims. Data privacy notes are presented, and questions are allowed before recording. The interview is recorded as a voice file.

I. Background and warming up (5-10 minutes)

1. What was your motivation to do a PhD? Why in this university? How did these expectations affect your experiences?
2. You have made this doctoral journey map in the workshop. Is it correct that you had NN supervisors and NN advisors in your thesis?
3. For how many years did you work on your doctoral thesis project?
4. At which point in your studies did the Covid-19 pandemic start?
5. Did you publish papers outside your thesis?
6. Did you advise bachelor/master theses?
7. When starting your studies, what kind of experiences did you have onboarding? Who participated in your onboarding?
8. How did you feel about starting your research project?

II. The journey map (70-80 minutes). Here the participant also has opportunities to add more content to their journey maps and add new things to the discussion outside the questions.

First, you have mentioned *[a situation on the journey map]*.

(Ask about each situation on the journey map: “Next, you have mentioned *[a situation]*.”)

9. What happened in this situation?
10. Why was this situation important and meaningful to you?
11. What did you learn in this situation? (If needed, specify e.g., skills, values, things that you learned to do...)
12. What kind of skills did you apply in the situation?
13. You have interpreted this situation as *[positive/negative/neutral]*.
 - a. Why did you give this interpretation of the situation?
 - b. Please, tell us more about what made it *[positive/negative/neutral]*.
 - c. (If positive/neutral, ask:) What supported your doctoral studies in this situation? How did it support your doctoral studies?
 - d. (If negative, ask:) What hindered your doctoral studies in this situation? How did it hinder your doctoral studies? How did you overcome the situation?

(Ask if a situation is related to the university environment)

14. Did you collaborate with someone during the situation? What kind of collaboration was it? / How did you collaborate with them? Did you receive help from others? / Did you offer help to others? How did the collaboration affect your doctoral journey?
15. (If needed, ask more specific questions to understand the details, e.g., was the collaboration happening at the individual/team level, and what kind of interdisciplinary aspects, if any, were included in the collaboration?)
16. Did your supervisor/advisor(s) support you during the situation? What kind of support was it? How did you experience the support?
17. Did you receive support from colleagues (etc. in your research team)? How did you experience the support?
18. Did you use any of this university's services during the situation? What kind of services did you use? How did you experience the support from them?

III. Summary and conclusion (5-10 minutes)

Thank you for your active reflection on your doctoral journey during the interview.

19. During the discussion, have any such things related to your doctoral journey come into your mind that you would still like to discuss?
20. (Going back to your motivation to do a PhD,) what were the biggest positive & negative surprises in the process?
21. Did we forget to ask something important?
(*stop recording here*)
22. Would you like to give any feedback for us concerning this interview?

If anything comes up afterward, you can reach us by email. Thank you for your participation!

Part 5: Data extraction

After the interview and the Zoom meeting, Zoom converts the recording. The audio file has been transcribed into a written format in-house using Speec2Text tool (Aalto University, 2025). Once the transcription has been completed, the original recording is removed. The quality of the transcription has been assured manually with human oversight.

For unclear sections of the transcription, brackets have been used to indicate missing information, e.g. [--] (00:05:32). However, often ambiguous or missing information can be found in the participant's Miro Board, such as proper nouns.

Once the transcription is finalized, notes about recurring themes and direct quotes that reflect participants' emotions or pain points are identified and collected into a separate file. These findings have been categorized to reflect each participant's motivation, the nature of academic advising, the level of community support, and other meaningful experiences.

Additionally, each Miro board is exported as a PDF file, and all the notes are exported as a CSV file.

#40

HELLO DOCTOR!

1. START WITH THESE WARM-UP QUESTIONS

My motivation for a PhD was:

~write here, what was your motivation for starting doctoral studies~

Who was the most important person to supervise your work?
(the main supervisor, a co-supervising lecturer / postdoc / industrial manager etc.)

~write the person here, please do not use names~

2. CHOP YOUR DOCTORAL JOURNEY INTO SMALL BITS

The more notes, the more we learn. Please list all things that contributed to your doctoral journey experience: things about research, identity, community and colleagues, news, resources, leaps, failures, everything that contributed to the experience. You can also add the relevant things outside work.

Documents, such as diaries, meeting memos, MyDialog documents etc. can greatly help with your work.

You can duplicate this sticky note (Ctrl+D) or create new ones of any color from the toolbar on the left

Activity, action, milestone, event, feeling, person

3. FINALIZING THE MAP

- First, place the notes into your map in a chronological order.
- Second, rank those notes and observations based on your experience. Nilsson's classification can be seen here
- Finally, draw a mood line based on your notes; what does the entire journey look like?

You can use this line object to draw the journey line (drag a single node to create shape)- remember to place both ends to their correct places.

Grade	Explanation
+3	Indivisible. The strongest form of positive contribution, in which the action is inextricably linked to the advancement of the thesis and/or wellbeing.
+2	Reinforcing. Aids the achievement of a thesis goal. One objective directly creates conditions that lead to the achievement of another goal.
+1	Enabling. Created conditions that further the research/thesis goal and/or wellbeing. The pursuit of this one goal enables the achievement of another goal.
-1	Constraining. Limits options on research/thesis goal. The pursuit of this goal sets a condition or a constraint of the achievement of research/thesis goal.
-2	Counteracting. Clashes with the research/thesis goal.
-3	Cancelling. Strongest form of negative interaction. This factor makes it impossible to reach research/thesis goal and/or strongest negative impact on wellbeing.

Figure 1. A journey mapping template in the Miro online tool.

References

- Aalto University, 2025. Speech2Text: Easy Speech Transcription.
- Følstad, A., Kvale, K., 2018. Customer journeys: a systematic literature review. *J. Serv. Theory Pract.* 28, 196–227. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSTP-11-2014-0261>
- Rosenbaum, M.S., Otalora, M.L., Ramirez, G.C., 2017. How to create a realistic customer journey map. *Bus. Horiz.* 60, 143–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2016.09.010>